

InnovaWood ²⁵years General Assembly

The European networking event for
Wood Research, Innovation and Education

5-7
MAY
2026

SAVE THE DATE

Tulln, Austria

2026
edition
PROGRAM

3-day programme at a glance

	Monday 4 May	Tuesday 5 May	Thursday 7 May	
Morning		Opening statements Networking session Keynote session	Plenary session and Executive Board election Deep networking session	Checkout Field visit by bus to wood construction and building sites in Vienna.
	Lunch and poster exhibition			
Afternoon		The future of the European wood sector world café Results and impact session	4 research stations Parallel R&I workshop sessions Closure of General Assembly	2 groups.
		19:00 Informal get together Skyline restaurant, Hauptplatz 14, Tulln (own cost)	18:00 Guided tour	17:00 Drinks at UFT Tulln 18:00 Barbecue at UFT Tulln
Evening				

Venue

[UFT - Universitäts- und Forschungszentrum Tulln](#)

(University- and Research Centre Tulln)
Universität für Bodenkultur
Konrad Lorenz-Str. 24, 3430 Tulln an der Donau

Information about the UFT [link](#)
Campus plan [link](#)

Getting from Vienna to Tulln

Tulln an der Donau (Tulln on Danube River) is easily reachable from Vienna. Regular regional trains (ÖBB) connect Vienna with Tulln (25–35 min), or 60–75 min from Vienna International Airport.

By car, the journey takes around 40–55 min.

Book your hotel

[Best Western Hotel Tulln](#)

 €129/€149/night incl. breakfast
Reserve by e-mail to info@hotel-tulln.at

BOOKING CODE: "INNOVAWOOD ASSEMBLY"

[Hotel Römerhof Tulln](#)

 €107/night incl. breakfast
Reserve by e-mail to info@hotel-roemerhof.at

BOOKING CODE: "INNOVAWOOD ASSEMBLY"

Using the booking code does **not** work via online booking platforms e.g. booking.com

Tulln

is the garden capital of Austria. Read more about the city and surroundings [here](#).

Day 1 - General Assembly

May 5, 2026

Tuesday

At UFT - Universitäts- und Forschungszentrum Tulln

08:15 **Registration**

09:00 **Welcome address**

[Wolfgang Gindl-Altmutter](#), Head – Institute of Wood Technology and Renewable Materials, Wood K Plus / BOKU,
[Mike Burnard](#), President of InnovaWood, [Uwe Kies](#), Secretary General of InnovaWood

09:10 **Programme and networking concept**

[Oliver Jancke](#), InnovaWood

09:20 **Opening statement**

[Georg Rappold](#), Austrian Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate and Environmental Protection, Regions and Water Management, chair of WoodPoP, the European Wood Policy Platform

09:30 **Forestry and wood research in Austria. Role and impact of Wood K Plus / BOKU**

[Christian Hansmann](#), Wood K Plus, [Wolfgang Gindl-Altmutter](#), Wood K Plus / BOKU

09:50 **Speed networking session**

[Radmila Ustych](#), InnovaWood

10:20 **Networking coffee break**

10:40 **Keynotes with integrated audience discussion**

Moderator [Mike Burnard](#), InnoRenew

Resource efficiency in technical terms

[Johannes Konnerth](#), BOKU

Resource efficiency socioeconomic and sustainability side

[Veronika Auer](#), Egger

Resource efficiency policy and JRC perspective

[Sarah Mubareka](#), JRC Joint Research Centre

12:00 **Lunch & Poster exhibition**

13:00 **The future of the European wood sector**

Moderator [Oliver Jancke](#), InnovaWood

- World café deep dives into the priorities relevant for society, research, industry, such as key research fields, opportunities and risks of transdisciplinarity, talents, funding strategies, etc.
- Formulation and ranking of answers to the main issues at stake, presentation of priorities

14:45 **Networking coffee break**

15:15 **Results and impact session**

Series of 2min pitches | Parallel networking sessions on each pitch

16:00 **Open networking or leisure time**

18:00 Guided Tour
[Die Garten Tulln](#)

19:00 Official Conference Dinner
[Gaumenweide inside Die Garten Tulln](#)

Shuttle service from hotels Best Western and Römerhof to Die Garten Tulln and back from 17:15 to 19:00 and 21:15 and 22:15.

Day 2 – Workshops and Deep networking

May 6, 2026
Wednesday

At UFT - Universitäts- und Forschungszentrum Tulln

08:45 **Go-to-seat coffee**

09:00 **General Assembly**

Activities and news

Adoption of resolutions

[Uwe Kies](#), Secretary General, InnovaWood

10:45 **Networking coffee break**

11:15 **Deep networking session “The power of questions”**

Moderator [Radmila Ustych](#), InnovaWood

12:15 **Lunch & Poster exhibition**

13:30 **Research stations at Wood K Plus & BOKU**

(4 x 15min rotation stations; plus 30 min to change stations)

Go-to-seat coffee

15:00 **Workshop sessions** (60min parallel sessions)

Bio-based glues – exchange on ongoing research

[Erik van Herwijnen](#), Wood K Plus

The cascade vs. reality – setting up an international training

[Barbora Starovicova](#), BFH

Circular Economy

[Erik Larnøy](#), NIBIO

EU Policies

[Vanesa Baño](#), InnovaWood

Wood clusters collaboration

[Višnja Koščak](#), Holzcluster Steiermark

16:00 **Report back from the Workshop sessions**

Closure of the General Assembly

17:00 **Open networking or leisure time with refreshments until the BBQ starts**

18:00 Dinner

Barbecue at UFT Tulln

No shuttle service this time

Day 3 – Field trips to Vienna

May 7, 2026
Thursday

Field trips will be full day, but offer the possibility to hop-off at any point during visits

07:00 Hotel check out → please check out already on day 2 to anticipate long waiting lines

07:30 Two separate buses from hotels Best Western + Römerhof to UFT

! 08:00 Start from UFT Tulln in two separate groups and buses, groups merge at 14:00

Group 1 [Christian Hansmann](#), Wood K Plus

09:00 – 11:00, Seestadt Aspern & HoHo Wien

Janis-Joplin-Promenade 28

- [HoHo Wien](#), with [Woschitz Group](#)
Wangari-Maathai-Platz 1-2
- [Seestadt Aspern](#), walking tour
- [ASP Wohnbau](#)
Maria-Tusch-Straße 6

11:00 – 12:00, Lunch Break

- Individual lunch (own cost) Hannah-Arendt-Platz

12:00 – 13:00, Bus Travel at Janis-Joplin-Promenade 28

13:00 – 14:00, Village im Dritten

Elizabeth-T.-Spira-Promenade 2

- [Construction Baufeld 11B](#) of [einszueins architektur ZT GmbH](#)

Group 2 [Višnja Koščak](#), Holzcluster Steiermark

09:00 – 10:00, OBENAUF Projekt

Herbststraße 3

- Construction site of vertical building extension by [OBENAUF](#)

10:30 – 12:00, Gleis 21

Buchholzgasse 12

- Innovative owner implemented construction project [Gleis 21](#)

12:00 – 12:30, Light Lunch Break

- Individual lunch (own cost) near Gleis 21

12:30 – 13:00, Bus Travel at Buchholzgasse 12

13:00 – 14:00, Village im Dritten

Otto-Preminger-Straße

- [Construction Baufeld 01](#) of [Hohensinn Architecture](#)

14:00 – 15:00, Village Anchor

- [Construction Baufeld 4B](#) of [Weissenseer Holz-System-Bau GmbH](#)

15:00 – 15:15, Bus Travel at Landstraßer Gürtel 51

15:15 – 16:45, Holzforschung Austria

Franz Grill-Straße 7

- Premises & labs of [Holzforschung Austria](#)

17:00 Final drop-off: Wien Hauptbahnhof (Vienna main train station)

End of excursions and program

InnovaWood General Assembly 2026

Organized and hosted by

Supported by

Main contacts

Oliver Jancke & Radmila Ustych, InnovaWood

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List of speakers and topics of day1

15:30 Results and impact session

Series of 2min pitches (30min) | Networking interactions on each pitch (30min)

1. Niels Vonk, TNO	BioBuilt: a biobased building material innovation centre
2. Mark Irle, ESB	EcoReFibre: wood products in post-consumer waste
3. Vivien Madi, HFA	Sustainable coating systems from tree bark for the transport sector (SuperBark)
4. Maud Chemin, FCBA	Project Robustoo
5. Francisco Tienda, TalTech	Non-destructive characterisation of reclaimed timber using ultrasonic tomography
6. Luis Suarez, CMD	ENERWOOD: Predictive intelligence for wood industry savings
7. Karin Sandberg, RISE	Security buildings with timber and biobased materials
8. Gerhard Gröll, HFA	Decking: Materials, construction, maintenance and long-term experience. 23 years research and knowledge transfer
9. Erkki Verkasalo, LUKE	Impactful regional RTDI development of wood-based sector in Eastern Finland: Puhtia, Kiertobio, Forest.Joensuu
10. Chris De Roock, Wood.BE	Living Lab Circular Wood Cluster Grensland
11. Barbora Starovicova, BFH	Indoor Wooden Surfaces – Increasing Service Life
12. Alvaro Picardo, Cesefor	SMURF The forest owners' project
13. Karoline Tomkowiak, PULS	Agro-waste-derived foams as sustainable alternatives to wood-based fibers
14. Indy Verheyen, HOGENT	Unlocking local and circular wood for high-performance timber windows